

TOWARDS AN EMPIRICAL MODEL OF THE UX: A FACTOR ANALYSIS STUDY

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ABSTRACT

One of the key factors to bear in mind when it comes to developing innovative products is a satisfying and pleasurable user experience (UX). Although there are many models and definitions of UX, most of them have been proposed intuitively. From themes and elements previously identified as essential for an UX model, a study of exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was performed. We found eight factors in Before-UX-stage, 7 in During-UX and 17 in After-UX stage. Similar UX aspects are expressed in different ways through the different stages and factors. There are differences in terms of how a factor could weight and relate to others regarding the UX-stage. Moreover, while some factors are consistent with the literature, others are new. Most of the factors give us an idea about the articulation of variables and the way some factors relate to others.

KEYWORDS: *User experience-UX, UX-elements, UX-model, factor analysis, empirical research.*

INTRODUCTION

To develop innovative products, one of the key points is to strive for a satisfying and pleasurable user experience, UX, (Cagan, Vogel, 2002; Desmet, Hekkert, 2007). UX is a new paradigm to add value and differentiation, offering a broader perspective of the functionality and usability, focusing on how to create richer user experiences (Wimmer, 2011). The UX highlights the non-utilitarian aspects of interaction, focusing on the user's affection, perception and meaning and the value of such interactions. Currently, since in many product categories functionality and usability are highly satisfactory aspects, competition is focused on UX (Cagan, Vogel, 2002, Kano, 1987).

An UX literature review was conducted for 2003 – 2013 publications. Ariza, Maya (2014) identified UX models and definitions with some key dimensions: the subjective, context dependent and dynamic character of UX (Hassenzahl et al 2006, Law et al, 2009). Despite this, it was not possible to identify empirically constructed models based on observations that account for, as widely as possible, the complexity of the UX. These models and definitions are mainly based on authors' self-reflections or insights (Desmet 2003, Mahlke 2005, Roto 2006, Hassenzahl, 2003). According to (Hassenzahl, Tracktinsky, 2006), this lack of empirical research restricts a theoretical advance and limits the UX concept understanding and its future development. As UX gains importance in many design disciplines, it also becomes more important to define, de-

limit, categorize and theorize about it, in an attempt to make it more precise, comparable, and generalizable (Kaye, 2011).

Here, we assume UX as: “*The awareness of the psychological effects elicited by the interaction with the product*” p.5, (Hekkert, Schifferstein, 2008). This broad definition allows us to account for the complexity we want to capture in our analysis.

This work is part of a wider research of which the final objective is the development of a prescriptive product design method, with an emphasis on rich experiential products. This method would fill a lack of relatively accurate, simple and quick methods suitable for three scenarios. First, in generating structured and rich ideas about experiential products in the FFE (Fuzzy-Front-End). Second, work as a conceptual design method of experiential products in companies with short product development cycles, without specialized personnel, few financial resources and where the risk level is low (i.e., SMES with low-volume production and high rotation products). In other words, this method would allow for designing a product with very little users' field-research. Third, heuristically support the design process in companies that develop their products using conventional UCD tools.

The first step of this research was to identify and categorize the information about UX. This revealed many items with distinct categories, hierarchies, and limits, making the situation poorly controllable because of its complexity. The need to identify what elements would be essential in a UX model with the product was evident (Ariza, Maya 2014). In that paper,

13 UX models, 10 definitions and 10 UX review papers, were selected out of 387 publications, to support the theoretical framework for the research. We applied to this set of data, the thematic analysis technique, TA. TA allows for the identification and structural analysis of information patterns, especially of a psychological nature (Braun, Clarke, 2006). As a result, we identified the essential elements, (grouped into general themes and specific elements or variables and sub-variables), which should be in a UX model. The second step, which we report in this paper, would be how, based on these results from the TA, to design an experiment and then apply a data reduction technique (factor analysis) to identify correlations between variables and summarize groups of variable factors. This step will allow us to undertake a validation of the elements found in the TA and provide evidence of how they are connected, i.e. to which extent they match the structure of themes and elements. The third step of the project will be based on the results of that experiment, building a detailed, complete, concise and manageable UX model. The fourth step, based on the proposed UX model, would develop the prescriptive method sought.

In the TA, eight main themes with their essential variables (28) were identified (Table 1). Although it was possible to identify themes that had been referenced in other UX models, some variables or sub-variables within each theme were different to those in the literature, which showed that they were overlooked or linked to different variables.

Thematic Analysis Results

Table 1 outlines the definition of the themes and variables that an UX-model should include. They were used to construct the research instrument. The discussion of all the themes is detailed in (Ariza, Maya, 2014).

In section 2 and based on the TA results, we explain the experimental methodology used to find relationships between variables. In section 3, how the results were analyzed and interpreted and in section 4, we present the conclusions.

METHODOLOGY

First, the experiment scheme was designed. Second, a stimulus (product for the experiment) was defined. Third, the data collection instrument (questionnaire) was designed. Fourth, the sample and the experiment conditions were set-up.

Experiment General Scheme

Exploratory factor analysis, EFA, was chosen as the technique to identify correlations and factors grouping variables. These types of experiments should be conducted in a naturalistic context to consider the environmental and social effects, but without interferences due to excessive noise or intrusions. Moreover, it should consider the UX dynamics: before-during-after and long-term stages interaction. The experimental protocol was as follows: 1. Explain the experiment to the subject,

THEMES	VARIABLES
User	Physiological aspects
	Concerns (motives, interests, emotional sensitivities)
	Affective appraisal
Product	Instrumental property (functionality, usability)
	non-instrumental (aesthetic, emotional, semantic)
Interaction	Active, passive
	Instrumental aspect (usability)
	Non-instrumental (aesthetic, emotional, semantic)
Context and external factors	Context: physical, social and use (situation of use)
	External Factors: social, tech, cultural, economic
Consequences	Behavioral
	Multisensory
	Cognitive
	Affective
Purpose of use	Purpose of action
	Purpose of being
UX dynamics	Before, during, after, over time
Total UX	Experience and continuous feedback

Table 1. UX Model Themes and Elements
Source: Ariza, Maya (2014)

2. Generate expectations about the product selected through visuals and video information, 3. Apply UX-Before questionnaire, 4. First approach to the product, allowing interaction for 2 minutes, 5. Apply UX-During questionnaire, 6. Second approach, longer interaction (8 minutes), 7. Apply UX-After questionnaire, 8. Check responses. All the experiment was run in Spanish.

Product definition

We selected a product with features that would allow us to evaluate instrumental and non-instrumental aspects. Cameras, headphones, desktop mouse, watches, smartphones, were proposed. We ruled out those products where technological aspects had a lot of weight in the final UX or that were too simple. Finally, headphones were chosen because they are useful and with a relatively complex usability and UX. Then, we looked for headphones references which, apart from their functionality, were rich in their non-instrumental aspects (aesthetic, emotional, social, etc.). The Sony WALKMAN® and MP3 player 4GB with Speaker (Figure 1), 3 in 1, NWZ-WH303

Figure 1: Product used in the experiment. (Source: Ariza)

headphones were chosen. This product was new to the market at the time of the experiment, comprising expectation and novelty, aspects important to UX.

Design of the instrument

We began with the operationalization of the variables identified from the TA. We reduced ambiguity by using the definition themes and variables. Possible variables dimensions and sub-dimensions were identified. In most cases, it was necessary to observe more than one dimension to describe the variable, see an example in (Table 2). The questions were evaluated on a 5-point Likert scale (1-Strongly Disagree, 2-Disagree, 3-Neutral, 4-Agree, 5- disagree). To facilitate the handling of the data, each question was coded. For instance, for “Have I known what to do with the product”, the variable “product” with dimension “Instrumental” and sub-dimension “usability” was coded (PIU1). Some survey questions were specific to the product category, for example, “Music is important to me” or “It has good sound.”

To improve the reliability and content validity of the instrument, we took as reference questionnaires such as SUMI (Kirkowski, 1993), AttrakDiff (Perceived hedonic and pragmatic quality, Hassenzahl, 2003), UEQ (user experience Questionnaire, Laugwitz, 2008). This also allowed us to identify the type of questions used when looking to find information about usability, pragmatic, and hedonic UX aspects. Another important consideration was to find a way to consider the dynamic characteristic of the UX. A longitudinal approach was proposed, where with the same product, we would seek to gather opinions and feelings at different times. Before-UX (early or imagined experience), During-UX: momentary (experiencing), After-UX: episodic UX (reflecting on the experience), and finally, Over-time-UX: a long term-cumulative evaluation as a collection of multiple periods of interaction (not taken into account in this study due to time constraints).

We generated more than 230 questions in a first phase. A refinement of the questions was made comprising: 1.Reviewing the definitions of the concepts proposed with the final items to ensure good relationship and more clarity, 2.Two pilot tests conducted with 3 students to ensure a good understanding of the questions, and, 3. Reducing the questionnaire with the help of an expert. The final questionnaire had 153 questions composed as follows: Before-UX: 28 questions, During-UX with 37, After-UX with 88. Not all questions applied for every stage; for example “Does it feel good in the hands?” did not apply for the Before-UX stage. The final questionnaire was uploaded to Google Drive App. This questionnaire gave us the data required for the EFA. As an example, (Table 3) shows the coded questions for the Before-UX stage.

VARIABLE	DIMENSION AND SUB-DIMENSION	SUB-DIMENSION CONCEPTUAL DEFINITION	ITEMS-(QUESTION-CODES)-UX-STAGE
Product	Instrumental (Usability)	The extent to which a product can be used by specified users to achieve specified goals with effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction in a specified context of use, ISO 9241-11	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Did I know what to do with the product? (PIU1) DuringUX 2. Did I find the product safe to use? (PIU10) AfterUX 3. Are the headphones simple to use? (PIU11) DuringUX 4. Could I identify how to activate all their functions? (PIU12) AfterUX 5. Was it clear to use? (PIU2) AfterUX 6. It looks complex to use (PIU3) BeforeUX 7. Supplementary product information is useful (PIU4) AfterUX 8. Was it easy to learn to use? (PIU5) AfterUX 9. I was worried about damaging the product in the interaction (PIU6) AfterUX 10. Using the product was quick and agile (PIU9) AfterUX <p>Note: similar questions were asked in different UX stages</p>

Table 2. “Product” variable operationalization example
Source: Ariza, Maya (2014)

QUESTIONS	ITEMS	CODE
1	I would buy this type of product to listen to music	UX5
2	Music has always been an important part of me	FC1
3	I could use them anywhere	CXL5
4	I like to find different ways to listen to music	CM2
5	I like listening to music	CI1
6	I like Electronic Products	CI2

Table 3. Example Items for Before-UX stage
Source: Ariza, Maya (2014)

Sample selection

A sample for EFA should take into account the ratio of subjects-number of variables. We followed the indications of Nunnally (1978), Guilford (1954) and Kline (1986, 1994) on this, and (MacCallum et al,1999) for advice on commonality issues. We had 153 questions representing 28 variables. So, a possible sample of N=200 would be about 7 times the number of variables. Despite these precautions, we were aware that this sample size could bring restrictions when it came to generalizing results beyond the studied population.

A convenience sample was selected: Colombian EAFIT university students, 17 - 25 year-olds, from engineering, management and humanities. Students studying product design engineering and music were excluded to prevent the introduction of bias due to their training.

The resources used for the data collection were: 3 research assistants (bachelor students), 2 headphones in their original case, tablets to answer the questionnaire (in Spanish), a product's brand promotional video and a product leaflet.

RESULTS

Data collection took 15 days, from Monday to Friday in the mornings and evenings, within the University premises (coffee shops, squares, and meeting points) to preserve a natural UX setting and in off-peak hours to minimize intrusions.

Preliminary analysis

200 people were surveyed generating 200 valid surveys: 23,5% from administration, marketing and business students; 50.5% from engineering students (7 programs), and 26% from other courses (communication, law, economics, accounting, geology). Capturing subjects in different places and times generated a good representation.

Firstly, questionnaire data were explored using SPSS for before-during-after UX stages and for the Total-UX, indicating whether the questions were unambiguous. Communalities were >0.64, therefore the N=200 was adequate to continue with EFA on SPSS.

Data Optimization

Firstly, we ran the EFA for the entire set of variables (Total-UX), considering very low or very high correlations (Field, 2009). Consequently, 14 variables (below $.3 > r > .8$) were removed. Secondly, a KMO test=0,678 indicated to continue the EFA. (Field, 2009).

EFA was then ran a second time, with a Total-UX 139 variables. After eliminating low correlation variables, and before finding factors, KMO raised to 0.76. Similarly the KMO >0.5 was checked again allowing us to remove 15 more variables. The definitive EFA was then performed with 124 variables.

EXTRACTION AND ROTATION METHOD SETTINGS

Two extracting factor methods are recommended in EFA to generalize the results to larger populations: maximum-likelihood and Kaiser's alpha factoring (Field, 2009). Both methods were run, but results implied increasing the sample size or looking for an alternative factor extraction method. As the former option was not possible, we used Principal Component Analysis, PCA, with Oblimin rotation, bearing in mind that the PCA's conclusions are restricted to the "sample collected and generalization of the results can only be achieved if analysis using different samples". It generated two factor matrices: the pattern-matrix defining the factors, and containing the weights for calculating the factor scores and the structure-matrix, visualizing the relationships between factors.

Factor Extraction-Interpretation

We took variances above 0.40. Well-defined factors have at least three items with heavy weights (Field, 2009). A screeplot and the Kaiser criterion allowed us to retain all factors with eigenvalues >1, with an exception: for Before-UX stage EFA, that having less than 30 variables, eigenvalues >0.7 are recommended (Field, 2009).

Factors structure

EFA was performed to the variables of each UX stage: Before-During-After and Total UX, (Table 4). KMOs >0.5 and determinant close to 0 for all the UX-stages, showed the suitability of EFA. The Bartlett sphericity test $sig=.000 < .05$, indicated correlated variables. After rotation, the factors selected accounted for over 65% of all the variance. Cronbach's alpha coefficient, $\alpha=0.92$ indicated good questionnaire reliability. Additionally, all factors had $\alpha > 0.80$.

The EFA statistical process won't be detailed. We focused on the interpretation and construct labeling of the factors. See (Tables 5-6-7). Some questions (variables) shown are the translation of the original textual form, but for space limitation, others appear as the key issue of the question. Moreover only the factor labeling and description of the Total UX are shown.

STAGE	ITEMS	DETERMINANT	SIG	FACTORS	EXPLAINED VARIANCE
Before-UX	19	0.000	0.000	8	75.4%
During-UX	33	2.454E-009	0.000	7	65,6%
After-UX	72	1.000E-013	0.000	17	69.2%

Table 4. EFA stages summary
Source: Ariza, Maya (2014), SPSS analysis

NUMBER	QUESTIONS	LOADING	FACTOR
1	I see myself using the product	,886	Anticipation to buy and use the product Factor. Reflects how the user envisages himself using and buying the product which motivates him to its use
	I'd buy this type of product to listen to music	,865	
	It triggers me to use them	,625	
2	I keep updated on technology issues	,893	Interest in the product's technology factor: Explains why the user is interested in technology and electronic products
	I like electronic products	,836	
3	It's a fashionable product	,792	Social approval factor: Represents the user's belief about the social acceptance of a fashionable product, linked to figuring out who would use the product
	I know what kind of people would use this type of product	,780	
4	I like listening to music	,902	Specific Concerns factor: Reflects the specific concerns attached to the activity performed with the product
	Music has always been an important part of my life	,867	
5	They look professional	,785	The professional look adaptability factor: Reflects how a product with a professional appearance could be used in any place
	I could use them anywhere	,706	
6	I'm feeling in a good mood today	,966	Mood factor: Reflects the user's current mood
7	The product looks valuable	-,850	The product value factor: Explains how given that the products is valuable for the user, she will be curious to find out more about it
	I am curious about the product	-,479	
8	The product looks attractive	-,793	Attractiveness-Interest Factor: Explains how an attractive product would be interesting and would entertain the user. Reflects the novelty value of the product as well.
	The product entertains me	-,620	
	I found the product Interesting	-,608	
	It looks novel	-,550	

Table 5. Before-UX Factors
Source: Ariza, Maya (2014), Factor labeling and interpretation

NUMBER	QUESTION KEY	LOADING	FACTOR
1	Exciting interaction	,740	The High Stimulation Factor: Influences the user to have an stimulating and fascinating interaction with the product, based on its impressive appearance; consequently the person gets into the product
	Fascinating	,632	
	Astonishing	,627	
	Been engaged	,519	
2	Knowledge to do	-,837	Complete Usability Factor: Influences all the user's usability concerns: to know what the product is for, to understand the conceptual model proposed by the product, control, to know if the user needs more to learn to use it, if the product is easy to use, if it is challenging, if the controls provide clear information and if it has been easy to learn to use
	Easy to understand	-,822	
	Control	-,786	
	More Information	,768	
	Simple to use	-,722	
	Challenging	,685	
	Works logically	-,629	
	Clear Controls	-,629	
Easy to learn	-,583		
3	Previous Experience	,772	Previous experience Factor: Explains that if the user has already used the product category or is familiar with it, it allows the person to imagine different things to do with the product
	Familiarity	,651	
	Imagine other uses	,587	
4	Harmonic form	,808	Aesthetic sensations Factor: Influences aspects of visual, tactile and kinesthetic aesthetics.
	Feels good in hands	,804	
	Feels good using	,752	
	Comfortable	,721	
5	Boring	,698	The Boring product Factor: Causes the perception of the product as boring therefore diminishing the user's interest and connection with the product
	Interested (Willingness)	-,494	
	Connection	-,476	
6	Different purpose	,854	The Multi-Purpose product factor: Reflects that the product has multiple purposes, especially those linked to its main practical function (providing good sound) and an aesthetic-semantic property (the product's originality).
	Good sound	,485	
	Originality	,434	
7	Easy to remember features	,537	Cognitive Ergonomics Usability Factor: Concerns the comprehension of the product functionality, the easiness to recall the product characteristics, its affordability All these aspects are correlated to an appreciation of how well the product fits to its design purpose.
	Clear functionality	,537	
	Invite exploring	,523	
	Fulfills design purpose	,487	

Table 6. During UX-stage FA
Source: Ariza, Maya (2014), Factor labeling and interpretation

NUMBER	QUESTION KEY	LOADING	FACTOR
1	Interested (Decision)	,754	The product engagement Factor: After the interaction with the product the user wants to gather more knowledge about it. This information would allow the user to anticipate and imagine using the product in the future. This would eventually lead her to buy the product. Those aspects are also correlated to a confirmatory belief of "I've found the product I was looking for!"
	Want know more	,678	
	Research more	,677	
	Buy product	,665	
	Imaging using	,575	
	Keep exploring	,488	
	Looking for similar	,436	
2	Quick, agile	-,786	The learnability Factor: Is at the basis of a user's assessment of product use, linked to the amount of time required to understand the product functionality and the clarity of its use. Finally, is correlated to the user's ability to explain the product functionality to someone else.
	Hard to understand	,721	
	Clear to use	-,669	
	Could explain	-,435	
3	Expecting more	-,758	Full expectations Fulfillment Factor: Reflects largely whether the product fulfilled the user's expectations: whether it surpassed the user's expectations and whether the product fulfilled what it claimed it could do.
	Cover expectation	,653	
	Fulfilled expectation	,594	
	Functional	,404	
4	Evocation	,727	Reminiscing factor: Reflects the remembering effects on the user after the interaction, thus generating nostalgia and the loss of the track of time
	Nostalgic	,654	
	Lost track of time	,553	
5	Make original	-,587	Self-image fitness with social context factor: Determines the user's self-perception as an original person if he uses the product. This is linked to envisaging the use of a more common product as a way to make him feel more comfortable. These aspects are correlated to imagining himself looking good if he uses the product, envisaging the product as a fashionable item and using it in different activities.
	Prefer common	,567	
	Make look good	-,456	
	Fashionable accessory	-,453	
	Using different activities	-,405	
6	Explore new uses	,612	The explorative use factor: Is at the basis of exploring new ways to use the product. This exploration entails some anxiety while using the product and surprise with some product functions. These aspects are correlated with a change in the way the user listens to music linked to feeling competent to use the product.
	Anxiety	,531	
	Surprise	,517	
	Change how one listens to music	,437	
	Competence	,416	
7	Disconnect from world	,819	Absorption Factor: Causes the user to disconnect from the world, and concentrating while interacting with the product. Those aspects are correlated to a further repeated product use and to fit the user's lifestyle
	Liked listen music this way	,577	
	Focus when interacting	,551	
	Repeatedly use	,493	
	Fit lifestyle	,474	
8	Icons recognizable	,851	Indicative Functions clarity Factor: Implies easily recognizing the product's icons and symbols linked to indications about the product use from the product or from its user manual. It entails the ability to activate all the product's functions.
	Clear Indications	,808	
	Useful (leaflet)	,504	
	Identification of functions	,418	
9	Use according to place	,765	Contextual knowledge Factor: Is at the basis of knowing how to use the product according to different contexts and to the integration of other (electronic) products the user has.
	Integrate with other products	,650	

10	Uncertainty	-,633	The starting point Factor: Reflects the clarity of knowing how to identify an "entrance point" to start interacting with the product
11	Brand association	-,835	Brand Awareness Factor: Makes possible the linking of the product to a particular brand
12	Technological consistent	,788	Technology advances assessment Factor: Implies an assessment of the product's technological advances. This aspect is correlated with a judgment about the product as providing an innovative way to perform its main function (listening to music).
	Innovative	,606	
13	Enjoy using in place	,747	Physical Context Enjoyment Factor: Determines product enjoyment in a particular context. It is related to the product likeability for the user's friends.
	Friends would like product	,467	
14	Original use	,582	Novelty in use factor: Influences the appreciation of the novelty of using the product'. It's related to the user's aesthetic appreciation of the product.
	Liked the look	,510	
15	Familiar style	-,753	Product Category Style Factor: Defines that the user will look for a style similarity between the product and others regularly bought.
	Communicate personality	-,466	
16	Change perception	,805	Product Perception Shift factor: Influences a change in the user's product perception after using it
17	Need explanation	-,481	Additional Learning Resources factor: Causes the user to ask for additional explanations or time in order to be able to use the product.
	Need time to understand	-,464	

Table 7. After UX-stage FA
Source: Ariza, Maya (2014), Factor labeling and interpretation

RESULTS DISCUSSION

Although, we started with a preconceived idea of how the variables should group, the statistical results from the EFA showed that some emerged factors were in fact consistent with the literature, for instance, the Complete Usability Factor or the Aesthetic sensations-Factor. On the other hand, most of the remaining factors gave us insights about the articulation of variables within them, for instance, the Product-engagement Factor shows motivation related to a pleasing encounter with the product and an invitation to explore or buy it. And finally, other factors showed themes like the Reminiscing-factor that were overlooked or not that common in the literature but that may be important for the UX.

There are some factors, for example, determining UX's aesthetic aspects that are expressed in different ways and ranked in different importance positions through the different UX-stages: for the Before-UX stage aesthetics appear as an Attractiveness-interest factor, for the during-UX stage appears as a pure Aesthetic-Sensations factor, and for the after-UX stage appears split on two factors: *Novelty-in-use factor* and *Product-Category-Style* factor. To understand the results, each factor labeling was created to reflect the underlying influ-

ences causing the answers pattern, explaining why it involves particular variables, rather than just describe them.

Despite the EFA extraction method restriction and the heuristic labeling, we believe in the importance of an empirical approach and the potential of these factors and their correlations (that are not reported here due to space limitations) to challenge the UX understanding, in order to contribute to further developments.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper's originality lies in the empirical approach, supported by EFA, to model UX while using TA results (that involved very distinct UX aspects), as input for the experiment. We believe that the structure of the factors accounts for UX complexity because the whole EFA was the final result of the revision of many key topics found in UX modeling publications. EFA allowed us to identify the latent variables or factors, behind UX, whilst allowing to tackle and manage UX complexity. The correlations between factors will give us insights of the variable relationships in the UX model sought and the derived further product design method.

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